

Utilizing Religion and Ethnicity for National Integration in Nigeria

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Abstract:

Basically, Nigeria is a plural society and heterogeneous in virtually all facets of life. The customs and traditions of Nigerians are so diverse to the extent that Nigeria as a country is now confronted with the problem of religion and ethnicity towards their political stability. The origin and history of ethnic conflict (societal wars and violence) can be traced from internal and external state rivalries to external (Physical) conflict. And its root cause is not very far from power competition and decision making over economic resources and other important human factor, like position. In general concept, the author of this paper argues that adherents of different religions and ethnicity buy and sell in the same market, join the same social organization or association, jointly establish corporative societies and guilds and often serve as business partners. In this way religion and ethnicity could be utilized for social integration. The study made use of participant's observation method and available written materials. The findings reveal that Nigerian problem is not ethnicity but rather the non-resolution of conceptual crisis where the state is more powerful than the people. Again, Nigeria has no shared core values. The paper concludes that there is the urgent need to resolve conceptual crisis between country, State and nation and equally enshrine National core values. Such values would guide future generation to prosperity, happiness, national integration and national survival. It recommends that with good leadership, religion and ethnicity, if properly taught, practiced, utilized and embraced could promote unity, national integration and national development. Nigerian problem is not religion and ethnicity but that of good leadership. We need a Servant-God-fearing leader not rulers.

Keywords: Utilize, Religion, Ethnicity, National integration, Country, State, Nation and Core values

Introduction:

In Nigeria, three things are intertwined: religion, politics and ethnicity; and the three are beclouded with corruption, poverty and insecurity. It is therefore difficult to solve one without considering all other underpinning factors.¹

Religious Factors: These include inadequate depth of understanding of both Christianity and Islam within and without these two religions; lack of knowledge and information on a popular level, particularly in local languages, of the scriptural-based condemnations of violence and terrorism in both Islam and Christianity;

statements and actions of a number of religious leaders both Muslims and Christians, which could be understood as undoing or encouraging violence; tensions arising from well-funded and organized foreign Christian missionary activity, and well-funded an organized Muslim missionary activity; and the actions and influence of Boko Haram and takfirs, and ideological influences upon the genesis of Boko Haram, revenge killings by some Christians for the deaths caused by Boko Haram.

Others include the actions and influence of gangs of Muslim youths carrying out organized killings of innocent Christians; the geographic polarization of Muslim and Christians along imaginary North-south fault line in the middle of the country, aggravated by demographic shifts and refugees movements in the period since independence; further geographical polarization of Muslim and Christians particularly within the Northern states where Christians residential areas (and in some cases local markets) and Muslim areas are

now segregated; Ineffective cooperation within Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIREC), relative to ten years ago.

Political Factors: Some of these are rampant corruption at every level among politicians; the long term and residual effect of the different ways that different parts of the country were administered during the colonial period, particularly between the North and the South; tensions between the respective roles of the Federal, State and Local government; problems arising from President Goodluck Jonathan continuing as President during the Northern unofficial “quota” of office (in the PDP ruling Party’s agreement) after the premature death of President Umaru Musa Yar’ adua, and the disputed question as to whether or not he is constitutionally allowed to seek a further term in 2015 Presidential election; tensions created by the statements and actions of Political leaders pandering to religions sentiments; and geographical and political interactions between Nigeria and neighboring countries such as Chad, Niger and Cameroun.

Others include the lack of ability or willingness on the part of government to consistently acknowledge all incidences of violence and to assist all victims; the lack of a clearly documented central and local record of all instances of social violence and their causes; the lack of ability or willingness to follow up on and carry out recommendations made by government appointed commissions which have investigated Communal crises; tension and competition between the traditional, tribal and ethnic leaderships and governmental and local leaderships and structures; government and Police neglect of violence and crime leading to a pervasive sense of insecurity; lack of timely response by government forces (Police and Military) to distress calls during times of violent conflicts; and the roles of some external powers and intelligence agencies within Nigeria.

Social and Ethnic Factors: These include pervading sense of fear due to insecurity and instability; the undermining and underfunding of traditional social, tribal and ethnic leaderships by the State and Federal Governments; residual tensions from the Biafra War or Civil War of July 1967 to January, 1970 particularly between the Hausas and the Ibos; tribal and ethnic disputes and cultural tensions; illiteracy and poor education ; drug abuse among sectors of the young ;the undervaluing of the role of women, particularly in conflict resolution.

Economic Factors: Some of these are the rampant neglect and mismanagement in various economic sectors even at the highest levels of government; the vast disparity between wealth, education, healthcare and employment levels in the “Muslims North” versus the “Christian South;” tension arising from Akwa Ibom, Rivers, Bayelsa and Delta states wanting bigger shares of oil and gas production, leading to disparity in the quantum of funds allocated to the states in the oil producing areas versus the states in the North, where no Northern states produce any oil or gas, and there is an over reliance on Federal allocation derived from oil revenue because of negligible internal revenue generation in states; the under development of a number of natural resources and sectors, example, agriculture and mining due to the focus on Nigeria’s oil wealth since political independence in 1960; poverty; unemployment and underemployment; land disputes, and lack of clearly demarcated grazing grounds for the nomadic Fulani cattle herders and their frequent clashes in Plateau, Benue and Adamawa states; lack of assistance on the part of government to victims of violence housed in refugee camps to enable them re-establish normal life.

Legal Factors: Perhaps, the biggest problem of all is the legal tension between the rights of “indigenes” and those of “settlers”. Each state has its own different and arbitrary definition of who is an “indigene” and who is a “settler” and each state sets its own arbitrary policies for favoring its indigenes in healthcare, public education, land distribution, jobs and other benefits; the lack of universal rule of law (yet, Nigeria is currently a non-permanent member of the Security Council of the United Nations Organization); widespread injustice by judiciary, the executive, the police and military; extra judicial killings, suppression and torture by police and military and lack of accountability and punishment for such nations;“ impunity,” the lack of willingness or ability to punish those directly or indirectly responsible for incidents of violence, especially when these are powerful personalities in the society; the little or poor person gets punished while the big or rich person is

unscathed.² Before we examine the ways and means by which religion and ethnicity could be utilized for national integration, it is necessary to give the operational definitions of our key words.

Definition of Concepts

“Utility” is the advantageousness, or benefit or convenience or efficacy or fitness or point or practicality or profit or serviceableness or usefulness of religion and ethnicity in uniting Nigeria as a nation; while utilized is used here to imply the appropriateness or usefulness of religion and ethnicity integrating Nigeria.³ “Religion” is used in this paper to refer to African Religion, Christianity and Islam-the major religions in Nigeria.⁴ “Ethnic” or “Ethnicity” refers to a race or the classification of humans into social, cultural groups, because of their distinctive character, spirit or culture while “Ethnicity” is the fact or state of belonging to a social group that has a common national or cultural tradition. In Nigeria, we have several ethnic groups but we share the same nationality.⁵ “National Integration” is the awareness of a common identity among the citizens of a country like Nigeria. This implies that though we belong to different castes, religions and regions, speak different languages, we recognize the fact that we are all one. This was one of the major decisions made by Nigerians prior to political independence on 1st October, 1960, that is, to become the Federal Republic of Nigeria, requires that Nigerians will be integrated with one another for the purpose of co-existence, unity, national integration and development.⁶ “Country” is a common wealth or kingdom or sovereign state with its own government, occupying a particular territory.⁷

“State” as used in this paper means a province or an area of land that is part of a Country. They are usually units of government.⁸ In Nigeria, we have thirty-six states and the Federal Capital Territory, FCT. “Nation” means a large body of people united by common descent, history, culture or language, inhabiting a particular country or territory.⁹ “Core Values” are the principles or beliefs that a person or organization view as being of central importance, example, wisdom, performance and love or success at work and in life. In Nigeria, there are internal crisis in resolving the differences between country, state and nation. As the result of such confusion, the country is often reduced to a state because often it looks as if the state is more powerful than the people; and even sometimes an individual behaves as if he or she is more powerful than the country. Until Nigeria builds a nation with shared core values, we cannot move forward and resolve our several crises. For instance, American’s core values are: Liberty, Self-government, Equality, Individualism, diversity and unity.

In Nigeria, besides sports, there is no shared core value like loyalty, character and service. “Loyalty” is commitment to the Nigerian nation and the people. “Character” on the other hand is the maintenance of the highest ethical standards and integrity; while “Service” is excellence in the formulation of policy and program management with room for creative dissent. “National Integration” refers to the process of building a just social unit which confers on every inhabitant within it a sense of belonging, a satisfactory level of participation in decision making and development; and a change to share from the resources of the society commensurate with decent and acceptable living¹⁰ in a secured society.

Utilizing Religions and Ethnicity for National Integration in Nigeria.

The interaction of religion is the interaction of people. There are three major religions in Nigeria. Adherents of Traditional religion, Islam and Christianity. Thus, we are confronted with the triadic experience of the Euro-Christian experience, Islamic experience and Traditional autochthonous indigenous Nigerian experience. There will be no religions without the people practicing them. Whereas there may be people without religions. When we talk of religions interactions therefore, we must take into consideration the people and their society generally.

The society is not an abstraction. It is a community of people united for the sake of their welfare. In National Integration, adherents of different religions must work for the total well-being of the society in all its spheres of activity and parameters. In nation building and national integration ethnic and religious sentiments are irrelevant because the head of the community cannot say that people who do not hold the same religions views as he or she

does, should not enjoy the facilities of such community. The community, state or country belong to all and sundry and as such, all must work together, for its growth, development and national integration irrespective of religious beliefs. Cooperation takes place at different levels. The environmental demands in trade, association, education, government, extended family situations, politics and many other situations bring together traditionalists, Muslims and Christians at various levels. Few instances will suffice.

i. Trade:

The adherents of different religions buy and sell in the same market, join the same social organization or associations, they jointly establish cooperative societies and guilds and often serve as business partners. Associations with cultural practices also bring interactions and national integration. Marriages, naming ceremonies, funeral ceremonies and the like are attended by Muslims, Christians and Traditionalists, irrespective of the religious beliefs of the celebrants.

ii. Politics:

In the area of Politics, Christians, Muslims and Traditionalists see themselves as brothers and sisters even where ethnic loyalty may play down on the spirit of oneness, togetherness and solidarity. Politicians of various religious affiliations hold rallies and conferences together and pass resolution in the interest of the masses. Indeed, such situations tend submerge religious distinctiveness in order to bring about good government and administration, as well as ensure the total well-being and national integration of the whole country. In the struggle for Political independence of Nigeria, all adherents of different religions worked together to ensure that reality on 1st October, 1960. Religious differences were deemphasized, ethnic loyalty was given little or no consideration. In nation building, while brotherhood and sisterhood in the family of one God was given the dominant place for the survival of our Great country, Nigeria. Nigeria belongs to all and sundry and not to Christians, nor Muslims nor traditionalists.

iii. State Functions:

Muslims, Christians and traditionalists engage in the same employment, social welfare, health services and industries. This is not a new phenomenon. In the Middle Ages, Jews Christians and Muslims worked together as monotheists and children of Abraham.¹¹

iv. Education:

Western Education has afforded social as well as religious mitting in Nigeria. Traditionalists, Muslims and Christians attend the same school without seeing themselves as enemies. Former classmates of different religions do business ventures together and promote one another in politics or the Civil service.¹²

v. Theological Levels:

Traditionalists, Muslims and Christians meet together in dialogues, conferences, seminars, symposia, workshops and even religious or social gatherings and emphasize what brought them together rather than what separates them. At the theological level, the tendency of "*Others have none and we have all*"¹³ is removed.

vi. Intellectual levels:

At intellectual levels, adherents of different religions ask for doctrinal statements, and examine the insights to which such statements point to. In this way, adherents of various religions see where the differing insights are contradictory and where they are complementary. By seeking insights in other religions, adherents learn from one another and put into play intellectual interactions. This process leads to national integration. There are equally evidence of inter – religious borrowing among different religions.

vii. Thaumaturgical Responses to Social Needs:

Every Nigerian apprehends evil in many different ways. The witch, the sorcerer, the evil spirit and all other sources of mishap haunt the world of Nigerians and so they look for relief from them in different forms of supernatural action.¹⁴ Again, the increasingly social and economic demands of the Nigerian society lead the citizenry to seek supernatural aid in business, employment, politics and other spheres of human activities. Thus, adherents of various religions seek salvation from God in different ways. Thaumaturgical

responses to human needs therefore, encourages unrestricted interaction between adherents of different religions.

viii. **Compromises and Concessions:**

Similar to thaumaturgical responses to human needs is the situation of compromises and concessions. In this case, we have people who are either traditionalists or Muslims or Christians but practice other religions as occasion demands. They are compelled to do so because of their occupations. Thus, hunters, blacksmiths, drivers and those who deal in iron may feel obliged to worship the god of iron. This shows that in the changing situation, people may practice traditional religion and other religions simultaneously and this brings people of different religions together.

ix. **Marriages:**

Marriage between people of different religions is common in Nigeria, especially those who are open minded. This brings national integration and religious harmony.

x. **Poverty:**

A more fundamental challenge to national integration manifests in poverty. Mass poverty is breeding ground for extremism-religious, ethnic and class-consciousness. It is a fact that the current depression in the Nigerian economy has rendered many citizens, especially youths idle and almost hopeless.¹⁵ Hence, they have become instruments of manipulation by the elites and the politicians for the religious uprisings in the country.

Recommendation and Conclusion

Let us enter one or two important Caveats. First, no religious understanding and cooperation can be achieved if we think that others must subscribe to our own religion. All religions must be allowed and encouraged to go on with their beliefs and practices. There must be no idea that a particular religion must super impose its tenets on others. People should not try to force or over-persuade into another religion. People on their own accord may find other religions more appealing to them and may want to join it. Religion should guide the human family into wholeness, we should therefore inspire wholesome respect for other people's religion so that religion may achieve this goal. As we come together and deal with one another, we should recognize each other as brothers and sisters, children of one God, whom we profess to love and serve.

Second, we should not scorn knowledge. Knowledge is sought anywhere and everywhere. We should try to dispel all ignorance and prejudices about other people's religions by a dispassionate and objective enquiry into the truth and values of their faiths. We should emphasize common grounds and aspects that unite us rather than that divide us. It should equally be noted that contacts with other religions make us feel a need for a better knowledge of our own faith. For when we know some striking truths revealed by such religions, we will find many occasions to speak with the adherents of those religions. And in the light of our new understanding of such religions, we shall be astonished to read some unpleasant utterances of the past about each other's religion, and we shall also feel the urge to cease paying attention to such insults and silly affirmations which are derogatory or false. In this way, religion will unite rather than divide us.

Nigeria is made up of many peoples, cultures, languages, ethnic groups and religions with rich histories and traditions. These wealth and varieties were brought together on 1st October 1960 with the hope of integrating with one another for the purposes of peaceful co-existence, national unity, national integration and socio-economic and political development. Unfortunately, religious crisis and ethnicity have made the concept of national integration look impossible. This paper argues that the things that unite us as a nation far outweigh those that separates and divide us. Therefore, national integration is non-negotiable and not a matter of choice.

The paper concludes that Nigeria needs a capable leadership that can tackle insecurity, restore public confidence in leadership, bring Nigeria from its consumerist to production economy, lift up the people's

sagging morale, credibility, accountability, productivity, a security provider and a leader with a touch of integrity. It recommends further that, the fight against corruption should be more urgent in resolution. It further argues that fixing today's Nigeria is beyond ethnicity, tribalism, religions and ethnicity. It recommends further that religion, ethnicity and national integration if properly taught, understood, practiced, utilized and embraced, can promote unity, national integration and national development.

In the traditional Nigerian societies, there was no unemployment. The end-product of education was to make an individual of good character in all things. "Good character" includes respect for old age, loyalty to parents and local traditions, honesty in all private and public dealings, devotion to duty, readiness to help the needy and the infirm, sympathy, courage, sociability and a desire for hard work.¹⁶ These could be enshrined in our constitution as national core values. Each individual should be encouraged to become a useful member of the community because the underlying goals are common to all – national integration and development.

Endnotes:

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